

Impact of Financial Management Strategies on the Profitability of Commercial Companies in the City of Lichinga

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the impact of financial management strategies on the profitability of commercial enterprises in the city of Lichinga, Niassa Province, Mozambique. This article aims to analyze the impact of financial management strategies on the profitability of commercial enterprises in the city of Lichinga using a mixed-methods approach. Data from selected companies were collected through questionnaires and interviews. The theoretical framework highlights some concepts of financial management, common strategies, and profitability indicators. The results reveal a significant and positive correlation between financial practices and company profitability, suggesting that companies that plan adequately, rigorously control costs, and efficiently manage credit exhibit higher levels of economic performance. Statistical analyses, including correlations and regressions, demonstrate that financial practices significantly explain the variation in profitability. The study concludes that strengthening financial management is a determining factor for the sustainability and growth of commercial enterprises in the city of Lichinga, recommending training actions for managers, the adoption of control tools, and improvements to internal management systems aimed at strengthening local management capacity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The city of Lichinga, located in Niassa Province, has a growing commercial sector characterized mostly by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which play a crucial and important role in local economic development. However, many of these companies face significant challenges related to financial sustainability and maximizing profitability. In this context, strategic financial management emerges as a determining factor for business success. This article aims to analyze the impact of financial management strategies on the profitability of commercial enterprises in the city of Lichinga. The research seeks to identify which financial practices are most effective, how they are applied in the local context, and how they contribute to the economic performance of companies. The relevance of the study lies in the need to strengthen the managerial capacity of local companies by promoting a culture of financial planning and data-driven decision-making. By understanding the links between financial management and profitability, it is hoped to provide support for entrepreneurs, company managers, and public policy makers. This research is scientifically relevant because it will contribute in some way to the advancement of knowledge in the areas of corporate finance, by empirically

analyzing how financial management practices influence profitability. From an academic point of view, this work strengthens the theoretical and practical understanding of financial management; in higher education, it serves as a basis for future research and as reference material for students and teachers in the areas of accounting, economics, and management; furthermore, it contributes to the development of analytical and critical skills related to financial decision-making. Within the scope Socially, this research is relevant because good financial management in commercial enterprises is reflected in the well-being of the community, generating jobs, economic stability, and a greater supply of goods and services. Economically, the research allows us to understand how efficient financial practices drive business growth, consequently boosting the local economy. Business profitability ensures business continuity, increasing tax revenue and stimulating investment, which strengthens the commercial sector and the country's economic fabric. Some limitations of the study include the sample not representing all commercial enterprises in the City of Lichinga, possible bias in managers' responses, and difficulty in accessing more detailed financial data.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Concept of Financial Management

Financial management encompasses the set of practices and processes that guide the efficient use of a company's economic resources. Generally, it involves decisions related to obtaining, applying, and controlling money, ensuring that the organization can remain stable and achieve its objectives. In small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), this process is even more important, as resources are often limited and financial risks are more sensitive. (Gitman, 2015 ; Kich et al., 2018) highlight that proper financial management depends on planning, monitoring, and continuous analysis, allowing for a balance between risk and return. This means that the manager needs to clearly understand how money enters and leaves the company, anticipating future needs and identifying potential imbalances.

Among the fundamental elements of financial management is cash flow, which in turn represents the inflows and outflows of financial resources in a given period. Rigorous control of cash flow helps prevent failures to meet obligations and facilitates the identification of investment opportunities. Similarly, the business budget allows for the planning of revenues, expenses, and financial goals, serving as a guide for strategic decisions and for evaluating the company's actual performance (Agustina, 2019) .

Another essential component is cost management, which helps identify waste, reduce expenses, and increase efficiency. By thoroughly evaluating costs, the company can better understand its operational structure and identify possible improvements without compromising the quality of products or services. Financial analysis, in turn, provides indicators that guide the manager in assessing economic health, enabling more informed decisions aligned with strategic goals (Müller & Kriger, 2017) .

In short, financial management is a strategic area that directly impacts a company's ability to generate value, maintain sustainable operations, and seize growth opportunities.

2.2. Common Financial Management Strategies

Companies use different strategies to organize and optimize their financial resources. Among the most relevant are:

a) Cost control

Cost control involves the systematic monitoring of operating expenses to avoid waste and improve profit margins. Techniques such as flexible budgeting, variance analysis, and comparison with market standards are widely used (Pasin, 2000) . These practices help detect deviations and correct errors, increasing the efficiency of internal processes.

b) Cash flow and liquidity management

Liquidity is necessary to ensure that a company can achieve its short-term goals. To this end, it is essential to monitor its operational and financial cycle, anticipating periods of greater pressure on resources . (Gitman, 2015 ; Roza, 2015) reinforce that effective cash management not only avoids insolvency but also allows companies to seize investment opportunities without compromising their stability.

c) Strategic financial planning

Financial planning involves setting goals, forecasting revenues and expenses, preparing budgets, and analyzing scenarios. Proper planning allows for aligning short-term decisions with the company's long-term objectives, adjusting strategies whenever necessary. According to (NICARETTA, 2023 ; Harris et al., 2007) , this process requires an understanding of the competitive environment and flexibility to adapt to economic changes.

d) Investment analysis

Investment analysis is used to evaluate alternative resource allocations and select projects that offer the highest risk-adjusted return. Tools such as Net Present Value, Internal Rate of Return, and Payback Period help compare projects and decide where to invest most efficiently . (Demarzo , 2023) highlights that, in addition to quantitative analyses, it is essential to consider macroeconomic factors, the market, and the company's strategic needs to ensure robust decisions.

2.3. Business Profitability

Profitability expresses a company's ability to generate profit from the resources it uses. Several financial indicators are used to assess it, including:

a) Net Margin

Net profit margin reveals what portion of revenue actually translates into profit. A high value indicates that the company controls its costs well and manages to maintain efficient operations. (Assaf Neto, 2012)

b) Return on Assets (ROA)

ROA shows how much profit a company can generate from its assets . It measures operational efficiency and indicates the return generated for each monetary unit invested in assets. However, the interpretation of this indicator must consider the influence of financial expenses, as these affect the final result (Assaf Neto, 2012) .

c) Return on Investment (ROI)

obtained in relation to the total resources invested. It is a simple and widely used measure in performance analysis, but it can be sensitive to factors such as asset obsolescence or lack of reinvestment (Wernke & Cláudio, 2003) .

d) Return on Equity (ROE)

ROE (Return on Equity) shows the profit obtained by the owners of companies for each monetary unit invested in their equity. It is an indicator valued by shareholders because it shows the company's ability to remunerate its partners. However, ROE can be influenced by financial leverage, which requires joint analysis with the cost of capital and the risk assumed . (Assaf Neto, 2012) .

2.4. Relationship between Financial Management and Profitability

The relationship between financial management and profitability is widely recognized in the corporate finance literature, being considered one of the pillars of business performance. Efficient financial management involves the planning, control, and rational use of financial resources ,

which is directly reflected in the company's ability to generate profits and remain strong in the long term. It guides decisions on investments, financing, and profit distribution, always seeking to maximize the company's value. When these decisions are well-structured—that is, when there is a balance between return, risk, and liquidity—profitability tends to increase. Several studies indicate that companies that adopt structured financial practices tend to show better economic performance because effective financial management contributes to cost and waste reduction, better use of investment opportunities, greater control over financial risks, and more informed and strategic decision-making (Gitman, 2015). In a context like that of the city of Lichinga, where many businesses are family-owned or informal, the adoption of financial strategies can represent an important competitive advantage. Thus, we can affirm that profitability is a reflection of the quality of financial management.

2.5. Previous Studies and Mozambique

Research conducted in other regions of Mozambique indicates that a lack of training in financial management is one of the main obstacles to business profitability. Training and technical support initiatives have shown positive results in improving business performance. They also provide clear recommendations for training in finance and budget planning, measures that managers and public policies can implement in the short to medium term to improve profitability. The authors show that companies that adopt organized financial practices tend to exhibit better levels of efficiency, greater operational stability, and improved adaptability to the local economic environment. Therefore, the implementation of financial training programs, improvements in internal control systems, and greater awareness of the importance of structured financial management are recommended.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Type of Research

This study adopted a quantitative approach, as it was based on the collection, processing, and analysis of numerical data related to financial management practices and profitability indicators of commercial companies in the city of Lichinga. This approach allowed us to measure the intensity of the relationships between the variables and the degree of influence of financial practices on economic performance.

3.2. Population and sample

The target population of the study consists of commercial sector companies located in the city of Lichinga. The sample comprised 30 companies, selected by convenience sampling, covering different segments such as food retail, construction materials, and clothing. The inclusion criteria were: companies with at least 2 years of activity, formal registration with the legal authorities, and availability of basic financial data.

3.3. Data collection instruments

This research utilized a structured questionnaire, developed based on the main dimensions of financial management and business profitability, applied to financial managers or owners. It contained questions about financial management practices, performance indicators, and challenges faced, with the aim of deepening the understanding of financial decisions and strategies adopted. The questionnaire was administered in person, ensuring greater rigor and immediate clarification of any respondents' doubts.

3.4. Analysis techniques

For the analysis and interpretation of the data, this research used quantitative analysis techniques. Initially, a descriptive analysis was carried out to characterize the main variables of the study. Subsequently, inferential analysis techniques were applied using Pearson's correlation coefficient, utilizing software such as R and SPSS, ensuring the rigor, precision, and replicability of the results. In addition, simple and multiple linear regression models were also used. This methodological approach allowed for an empirical understanding of how financial management practices influence the economic performance of commercial companies in the city of Lichinga.

4. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS.

This section aims to present and interpret the main results obtained from the analysis of information collected from commercial companies in the city of Lichinga. The objective was to understand how the financial management strategies adopted influence the profitability and economic performance of local organizations.

This study consisted of data collected from 30 commercial companies located in Lichinga City. The variables analyzed included financial management strategies such as financial planning, cost control, and credit management, as well as profitability indicators such as Return on Assets, Return on Equity, annual profit, and net margin. The results indicate that most companies adopt some level of financial planning, although with varying degrees of formalization. It was also observed that companies with more structured cost control, budget planning, and credit management practices generally show better economic performance indicators. Regarding profitability, the values of ROA, ROE, Net Margin, and Annual Profit vary significantly between companies, reflecting differences in management models and the effectiveness with which resources are used. Statistical analyses confirm a significant positive correlation between the implementation of financial management strategies and profitability indicators, indicating that better financial practices are associated with higher business performance.

Fonte: Autora

Figure 1: Distribution of companies by sector of activity

Fonte: Autora

Figure 2: Distribution of Financial Indicators

Correlation Matrix between financial practices and profitability indicators

```
> cor(vars, use = "complete.obs")
```

	margem_liquida_pct	ROA_pct	ROE_pct	ROI_pct
margem_liquida_pct	1.0000000	0.7289684	0.49353448	0.22945035
ROA_pct	0.7289684	1.0000000	0.92596953	-0.01167390
ROE_pct	0.4935345	0.9259695	1.0000000	-0.00562928
ROI_pct	0.2294503	-0.0116739	-0.00562928	1.0000000

Multiple regression model

```

Call:
lm(formula = ROE_pct ~ margem_liquida_pct + ROA_pct + ROI_pct,
    data = dados)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-6.9508 -2.6657  0.1242  1.5069  8.6788

Coefficients:
                Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      6.950361   1.786053   3.891 0.000907 ***
margem_liquida_pct -0.519804   0.101288  -5.132 5.08e-05 ***
ROA_pct           1.703369   0.114575  14.867 2.84e-12 ***
ROI_pct            0.005458   0.002916   1.872 0.075956 .
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 4.399 on 20 degrees of freedom
(6 observations deleted due to missingness)
Multiple R-squared:  0.9385,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.9292
F-statistic: 101.7 on 3 and 20 DF,  p-value: 2.796e-12
    
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5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results obtained revealed that financial management practices play a decisive role in the profitability of commercial companies in the city of Lichinga. The data demonstrate that companies that adopt more organized methods of financial planning, cost control, and credit management exhibit superior levels of economic performance. This result indicates that the existence of structured financial processes contributes not only to operational stability but also to the ability of these companies to generate higher returns. Thus, it is confirmed that financial management does not function merely as an administrative activity but as a fundamental strategic element for the growth and sustainability of companies.

The correlation matrix reveals that Net Margin shows a strong correlation with ROA ($r = 0.73$) and a moderate correlation with ROE ($r = 0.49$), indicating that higher operating profitability tends to increase return on assets and, to a lesser extent, return to shareholders. A near-perfect correlation is also observed between ROA and ROE ($r = 0.93$), demonstrating that asset performance directly influences return on equity. On the other hand, ROI shows very weak or practically zero correlations with all other indicators ($|r| < 0.23$), suggesting that return on investment follows its own dynamics and does not depend linearly on profitability or operating efficiency. This pattern indicates that Net Margin, ROA, and ROE are strongly interrelated, while ROI behaves as a more independent indicator within the financial analysis. The multiple regression model reinforced these conclusions by demonstrating that financial factors explain a substantial proportion of the variation in profitability, with values around $R^2 = 0.9385$. Among the predictors, ROA stands out as the most important factor, with a positive and highly significant coefficient ($\beta = 1.703$; $p < 0.001$). This indicates that increases in return on assets produce substantial increases in return on equity, reinforcing that operational efficiency is the main determinant of ROE. Net margin, on the other hand,

presents a negative and significant coefficient ($\beta = -0.520$; $p < 0.001$), suggesting that, when controlling for ROA and ROI, companies with higher margins tend to have lower ROE – a result that may indicate cost structure trade-offs or leverage effects. ROI, in turn, has a positive, but marginally significant effect ($p \approx 0.076$), not being as robust a predictor as the others. The adjusted model presents a very low residual standard error (4.39) and a highly significant F- statistic ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the combination of the three variables significantly contributes to explaining ROE. These results suggest that ROE depends not only on the profitability of assets, but also on combinations of operational efficiency, investment management, and profit structure. Thus, the multiple model offers a more complete and robust explanation of return on equity when compared to the simple model.

The discussion also highlights the heterogeneity observed among the companies in the sample. While some demonstrated high levels of financial maturity with well-defined processes and implemented control tools, others presented significant weaknesses such as a lack of formal planning, empirical management of cash flows, and poor monitoring of operational costs. These limitations help explain the reduced profitability of some companies, reinforcing the need for capacity building and skills development in the financial area. Thus, the results suggest that strengthening financial practices can be a decisive factor in increasing the competitiveness of companies, especially in a commercial market like Lichinga, characterized by high competition and resource limitations.

In summary, the discussion of the results confirms that efficient financial management is a key determinant of business performance in the commercial sector in Lichinga. The statistical evidence presented demonstrates that improvements in financial processes not only accompany but directly influence profitability, indicating that interventions in this area can generate a significant and sustainable impact.

Therefore, the research reinforces the need for the implementation of more rigorous financial practices, the adoption of modern tools, and the continuous development of management skills as a way to increase the economic performance of companies in the region.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study demonstrates that financial management is one of the main determinants of business profitability, especially in the context of commercial companies in the city of Lichinga, where the challenges of access to credit, technical training of managers, and strategic planning are significant. Financial management strategies, when properly applied, including budgetary control, treasury management, cost analysis, investment planning, and a balanced capital structure, have a positive and direct impact on profitability indicators such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

Analysis of previous studies conducted in Mozambique shows that companies implementing consistent financial practices tend to exhibit better economic performance, greater operational sustainability, and a greater capacity to adapt to local market fluctuations. However, many companies in the city of Lichinga still face structural limitations, such as a lack of training in business finance, poor access to modern financial instruments, and a deficient planning culture, which restricts the full utilization of available resources.

It is concluded, therefore, that strengthening financial management should be a strategic priority for commercial companies in Lichinga in order to improve the efficiency of asset utilization, reduce operating costs, and enhance profitability. Finally, it was acknowledged that this study has some limitations, such as the small sample size and the reliance on self-reported data, but it still contributes significantly to understanding the financial dynamics of companies. Future studies could include a larger number of companies, incorporating variables such as access to bank credit, management technology, and the economic environment, as well as applying comparative methodologies with other provinces or sectors. Investment in the financial training of managers, the adoption of internal control policies, and the use of financial analysis tools as an integral part of the decision-making process, as well as the implementation of rigorous cost control systems, are recommended. Thus, the integration of effective financial management and well-defined business strategies represents a solid path to the sustainable and competitive growth of the commercial sector in Niassa Province.

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